

A low-code machine learning library in Python applied to classify and interpret data of patients with Parkinson's disease using voice records

Daniel Hilário da Silva
Programa de Pós-graduação em
Engenharia Biomédica
Universidade Federal de Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brasil
ORCID: 0000-0002-0800-065X

Caio Tomus Ribeiro
Programa de Pós-graduação em
Engenharia Biomédica
Universidade Federal de Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brasil
ORCID: 0000-0003-0085-317X

Adriano Alves Pereira
Faculdade de Engenharia Elétrica
Universidade Federal de Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brasil
ORCID: 0000-0002-1522-9989

José Renato Munari Nardo
Programa de Pós-graduação em
Engenharia Biomédica
Universidade Federal de Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0009-0007-9355-7228

Leandro Rodrigues da Silva Souza
Programa de Pós-graduação em
Engenharia Biomédica
Universidade Federal de Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0003-2477-6893

Resumo — Parkinson's disease (PD) affects a large number of individuals globally, it is the second most common neurodegenerative disease after Alzheimer's disease and its early detection is crucial for effective treatment. Vocal disorders can often be detected in PD patients during the initial stages, in approximately 90% of PD patients, but the current diagnostic process relies heavily on subjective medical observations. To address this, machine learning (ML) methods have been implemented to classify and differentiate PD levels more objectively. In this study, we utilized the PyCaret library, an open-source, low-code ML tool in Python, to explore its benefits in classifying PD patients. We applied 16 algorithms from the PyCaret library for classification, to a database of voice recordings from healthy individuals and PD patients sourced from a public repository. Among the algorithms, Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), Support Vector Machine – Linear Kernel (SVM), and Gradient Boosting Classifier (GBC) demonstrated the best performance for the testing data. Additionally, we employed feature selection and hyperparameter tuning to enhance model accuracy. The results showed that the low-code ML models could be highly accurate in identifying PD patients through voice analysis. This application of ML in diagnosing PD can significantly support clinical decision-making and improve the precision of interventions, providing valuable assistance to healthcare professionals in patient care.

Keywords — *machine learning, medical diagnosis, PyCaret, Parkinson's disease, voice signal.*

I. Introduction

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a neurological disorder characterized by typical clinical signs and symptoms, including bradykinesia, tremor, postural instability, and muscular rigidity [1]. Additionally, PD affects approximately 10 million people worldwide [2], with its global burden doubling over the past 25 years due to increased longevity and longer disease duration [3], [4]. It is the second most common neurodegenerative disease [5].

Non-motor symptoms are prevalent in PD and exhibit characteristics that are less frequently observed in the condition. These symptoms encompass autonomic dysfunction, neurobehavioral disturbances, cognitive impairments, and sensory and sleep abnormalities [4].

Furthermore, Jankovic (2008) [1] identified four main features of PD, which can be collectively summarized under the acronym TRAP: resting tremor, rigidity, akinesia (or bradykinesia), and postural instability. Additionally, flexed posture and motor freezing have been included among the classic features of parkinsonism [1], [2], [5].

The primary factor contributing to the risk of PD is advancing age [6], thus leading to an anticipated surge in its prevalence in the forthcoming years due to the aging population [4], [7]. Concurrently, concerns and obligations arise regarding the necessity for early and dependable diagnosis of these conditions, propelling the development of tools that aid in prognosticating disorders that may compromise the well-being of affected individuals [3], [8].

Consequently, the identification of novel diagnostic indicators for PD or the enhancement of the precision of presently accessible tools becomes imperative, particularly in the initial phases of the disease [5], [9], as it is believed that the disease emerges well before the onset of motor symptoms, often characterized by olfactory loss or diminution, sleep disturbances, tremors, and decelerated movements [10]. In this context, non-invasive speech assessments have been explored as a promising marker for the disease, given that speech impairment, classified as one of the motor symptoms of PD, is consistently observed in approximately 90% of PD patients [5], [10].

The field of Machine Learning (ML) is a subdomain of Artificial Intelligence (AI) that explores computers' ability to learn from past experiences. ML models are constructed using a substantial amount of data, which is trained through mathematical and statistical approaches, enabling classification, clustering, and prediction of new data [11], [12]. In this context, the utilization of ML algorithms can facilitate the identification of relevant features to represent voice-related information in individuals with PD, achieved through data classification via feature extraction.

The integration of state-of-the-art technologies holds the promise of revolutionizing healthcare, paving the way for more personalized and precise approaches to patient care. Embracing the potential of ML algorithms in classification offers an exciting avenue for uncovering the most effective combination of clinically relevant spatiotemporal features to accurately diagnose and treat individuals with PD.

In this regard, this study aims to contribute to the clinical domain by presenting a low-code tool that employs simple-to-implement and optimized classification models, potentially assisting in early PD diagnosis based on voice recordings from patients. The research utilizes real-world PD diagnoses from a publicly available repository, in conjunction with ML models created using algorithms available in the PyCaret library.

II. Materials and Methods

This section provides comprehensive details on the study's participants, including information on speech recordings, data preparation, feature extraction, as well as the cross-validation methods and functions used for model analysis.

A. Dataset

The data used in this study are available in the public repository UCI Machine Learning Repository, which is a collection of databases used by the ML community for empirical analysis of Machine Learning algorithms [13].

The research protocol for data collection used in this study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Extremadura in Spain, and all participants provided informed consent. Individuals with PD who volunteered for data collection were members of the Regional Association for Parkinson's Disease in Extremadura [2]. A total of 80 individuals over the age of 50 were included in the study, distributed as shown in Table I.

TABLE I. Distribution of the participants of the study

	Healthy Controls (HC)	PD	Total
Recording number	40	40	80
Participants			
Sex			
Male	22	27	49
Female	18	13	31

The mean age (\pm standard deviation) of the participants was 66.38 ± 8.38 . In the dataset, 240 records were observed, considering 80 subjects with 46 variables in total, 44 variables with data over the voice, and three variables with data over the code, genre, and status of each individual.

Each row of the dataset represents one voice recording, and it was obtained by asking the participants to produce a specific speech sustaining the intonation of the vowel /a/ for at least 5 s. Second the authors three recordings were made for each participant and the voice samples were obtained through digital recording performed at a sampling rate of 44.1 kHz and 16-bit resolution using Audacity software version 2.0.5 [2], [14]. Patients with PD presented, according to the authors, at least two of the following symptoms: tremor at rest, bradykinesia, or stiffness [2].

B. Framework for classification modeling

In this study, for supervised ML modeling, a large number of algorithms, 16 in total, widely reported in the literature [5], [10], [15]–[17] for PD classification, and available in the PyCaret library by default as setup functions, were adopted in a comprehensive approach.

Different ML models were employed, and Figure 1 shows the ML framework proposed for the selection and evaluation of these models.

Figure 1. Framework for machine learning modeling for PD classification using voice records.

The proposed ML framework uses 44 acoustic characteristics as predictor variables (zero mean, unit variance), the variable genre, and disease status as response variables. The labels for the cases are 0 for HC and 1 for PD patients, respectively [2], [5].

C. Data preprocessing techniques

The dataset was imported as a CSV file, comprising 120 records for PD and 120 for HC, as indicated by the "status" column, using the Pandas library of the Python programming language. This allowed us to identify the data's balance and proceed with further analysis. Next, unnecessary variables 'ID' and 'Recording' were removed from the dataset before presenting them to the ML models. Subsequently, the acoustic variables data were normalized (zero mean, unit variance) using the StandardScaler function from the Scikit-learn library. Data normalization using the z-score technique was employed to ensure equal weighting of all features during the model learning phase [3]. This step was crucial since the dataset consists of multiple features with different scales, ensuring that each feature contributes equally to the learning process [9].

D. Initializing the dataset techniques

With the data prepared, we proceeded to use the setup function to configure the data for model training. This versatile function offers a wide range of parameters, allowing for the creation of a comprehensive data preprocessing pipeline. Upon execution, it generates a valuable table with detailed explanations of its settings and parameters [18], [19].

E. Classification Models

Considering the studies presented in the literature [5], [9], [15], [17], [20]–[22], we adopted a comprehensive supervised machine learning approach, employing 16 algorithms available in the PyCaret library by default to

classify data [19]. Our framework resembles that used in a previous study [3]. The algorithms applied to the training data encompassed AdaBoost Classifier (ADA), CatBoost Classifier (CATBOOST), Decision Tree Classifier (DTC), Dummy Classifier (DUMMY), Extra Trees Classifier (ETC), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBOOST), Gaussian Process Classifier (GPC), Gradient Boosting Classifier (GBC), K Neighbors Classifier (KNN), Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LGHTGBM), Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), Logistic Regression (LR), Naïve Bayes (NB), Quadratic Discriminant Analysis (QDA), Random Forest Classifier (RF), Ridge Classifier (RIDGE), and Support Vector Machine-Linear Kernel (SVM).

F. Training and optimizing the models

After initializing the data using the setup function, the training of models can be performed using the `compare_models` function from the PyCaret library. This function simplifies the process of selecting the best classification model by training all available models and presenting the results in an easily understandable format [19]. The output includes model names in the first column, followed by various performance metrics being the accuracy of our preferred model. The `create_model` function is utilized to train a targeted model, utilizing the parameters specified in the setup function. This crucial step ensures the model is trained with the appropriate data configurations established during the setup phase [18], [19].

Subsequently, the `tune_model` function plays a crucial role in improving the classification model's performance through hyperparameter tuning [18]. This technique aims to find the optimal combination of hyperparameters for the model. As emphasized by Ali (2020) [19], the `tune_model` function fine-tunes the hyperparameters of a designated estimator.

G. Analyzing the models

The `plot_model` function allows for the creation of various informative graphs for classification models. In this paper, we utilized this function to generate plots for the top three classification models [19]. These visualizations offer valuable insights into the performance and characteristics of the models, enabling a comprehensive analysis and comparison of their effectiveness in handling the given dataset [18]. For each algorithm, the confusion matrix was calculated, which is a matrix of actual and predicted values describing the classifier's performance. Each predicted value or class is compared with its actual class, thus determining the number of samples classified incorrectly and correctly, as shown in Table II. From the confusion matrix, various metrics can be extracted, such as accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and precision [23].

TABLE II. PD and Health Confusion Matrix

	Predict Value	
	Healthy Control	PD
Healthy Control	TN	FP
PD	FN	TP

In this study, the TP values represent patients correctly diagnosed with Parkinson's disease, while the TN values correspond to healthy patients accurately identified. On the other hand, FP values indicate healthy patients misclassified as having Parkinson's disease, and FN values represent patients with the disease incorrectly labeled as healthy by the model. [15], [24]. The model with the highest accuracy generated a Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve, visualizing the true positive rate (TPR) on the y-axis and the false positive rate (FPR) on the x-axis [25]. The ROC curve offers a comprehensive view of the classification model's predictive performance across various thresholds, enabling a global assessment of the diagnostic test's value by computing the Area Under the Curve (AUC).

The feature importance plot is a powerful tool for comprehending the variables (or features) that hold greater influence in the model's decision-making process. This visualization illustrates the relative contribution of each feature to the model's predictive capability [3]. The significance of this plot lies in providing valuable insights into the most relevant variables for the model, thereby playing a more substantial role in data classification or regression. It aids data scientists in identifying which features have a more pronounced impact on the model's performance and facilitates feature selection tasks, should simplification and efficiency enhancement be desired [18], [19].

H. Deploying the models

The `predict_model` function available in the PyCaret library serves the purpose of predicting outcomes for new and unseen data using a pre-trained machine learning model. Prior to employing `predict_model`, it is essential to have the model trained and optimized using the `create_model` and `tune_model` functions, respectively. The primary objective of the `predict_model` function is to expedite the application of a trained model to novel data for prediction purposes. This streamlined process is particularly advantageous in real-world scenarios, such as production environments or when dealing with real-time data, where prompt and efficient predictions are crucial [18], [19].

III. Results

In the pre-processing of the data, specific libraries were implemented that aim to simplify the process of initial treatment of the data, using functions of the Pandas library and standard functions of the Python programming language. The data referring to the acoustic variables were normalized by means of the `StandardScaler` function of the Scikit-learn library since the variables "ID" and "Recording" were removed and the status variables, which are our target variable and the genre variable, were inserted later in the final dataframe. After the preprocessing stage, the data needs to be passed to the setup function of the PyCaret library, where it is advisable to configure some initial parameters for this function.

```
## Initializing the experiment.
setup_class = setup(data=df_final,
target = 'Status',
train_size = 0.80,
session_id = 1245,
fold_strategy = 'stratifiedkfold',
fold = 9, feature_selection = True,
n_features_to_select = 0.35)
```

In the setup process, we specified the dataset name and the target variable, which, in this case, is the 'Status' variable. Additionally, we defined a crucial hyperparameter to split the data into two sets: 80% for training data and 20% for testing data. This careful division was implemented to avoid both under-fitting and over-fitting, following guidelines from [9], and a similar approach observed in [3], [15]. We chose the parameter `fold_strategy = stratifiedkfold` with 9 folds. The `Stratifiedkfold` is a valuable option to ensure that cross-validation is performed in a balanced and representative manner, making the model training process more robust and reliable. Additionally, we applied the parameter `n_feature_selection`, and we set the number of features to 0.35, reducing the number from 46 to 16 features that were presented to the models.

This function initializes the experiment in PyCaret and prepares the transformation pipeline based on all the parameters passed in the function. The setup function must be called before executing any other function [18], [19]. The command that generates the dataframe with the result of the model analysis over the training data is given by:

```
## Comparing the classification models
compare_models()
```

The results of this command are displayed in Table III, which presents the models' performance based on metrics such as Accuracy, Recall, Precision, and F1-Score, all presented in percentage. Additionally, Matthews's correlation coefficient (MCC) [17] which is defined within the interval, is also included in Table III.

TABLE III. Mean of Accuracy, Recall, Precision, F-Score and MCC of the 16 ML Models Applied to Training Data

Model	Training Data				
	Acc. (%)	Rec. (%)	Prec. (%)	F1 (%)	MCC [-1,1]
KNN	82.80	81.21	84.04	82.41	0.6588
LIGHTGBM	82.78	81.11	85.18	82.30	0.6678
RIDGE	82.30	83.33	82.24	82.54	0.6485
ETC	82.30	79.09	85.45	81.58	0.6546
LDA	82.28	82.22	82.79	82.30	0.6472
CATBOOST	81.79	79.09	84.66	81.21	0.6444
RFC	80.21	76.97	83.06	79.51	0.6101
LRC	80.18	78.08	82.07	79.66	0.6079
XGBOOST	80.18	77.88	82.37	79.62	0.6096
NB	79.22	79.19	79.80	79.08	0.5892
ADA	78.14	81.11	76.89	78.58	0.5685
GBC	78.09	77.98	79.37	78.09	0.5705
SVM	76.02	79.19	75.66	76.89	0.5266
QDA	75.52	73.03	78.59	74.67	0.5205
DTC	69.29	68.99	69.94	69.20	0.3889
DUMMY	48.41	33.33	15.87	21.51	0.0000

With the insights provided by Table III, it becomes feasible to gain an understanding of which models demonstrate superior performance on the training data. This progress enables the next step, which involves crafting specific models to undergo hyperparameter optimization before being evaluated on the testing data, characterized by the dimensions (48, 16).

```
##### Creating the Top 3 models #####
gbc_model = create_model('gbc', verbose=False)
svm_model = create_model('svm', verbose=False)
lda_model = create_model('lda', verbose=False)
```

After creating the models, it is possible to make the optimization and prediction process of them.

```
##### Tuning the Top 3 models #####
tuned_gbc = tune_model(gbc_model, verbose=False)
tuned_svm = tune_model(svm_model, verbose=False)
tuned_lda = tune_model(lda_model, verbose=False)
##### Predicting the Top 3 models #####
predict_model(tuned_gbc)
predict_model(tuned_svm)
predict_model(tuned_lda)
```

Now the models can be shown to the unseen data that is in this study, which is testing data. The Table IV presents the models with the best results from the testing data after the use of the `predict_model` function.

TABLE IV. Results of punctual verification of models.

Model	Accuracy (%)	Prec. (%)	Rec. (%)	F1 (%)	MCC [-1,1]
LDA	85.42	81.48	91.67	86.27	0.7139
GBC	83.33	83.33	83.33	83.33	0.6667
SVM	83.33	78.57	91.67	84.62	0.6761

The results presented in Table IV are obtained considering the values given by the confusion matrix, which is generated by the simple command for a specific model.

```
## Plotting the Confusion Matrix
plot_model(tuned_lda, plot='confusion_matrix')
```

The confusion matrix given in Figure 3 represents the results for the LDA model after the process of optimization by the function `tune_model`.

Figure 2. Confusion Matrix of the LDA model.

The command to generate the ROC Curves is as simple as the others.

```
## Plotting the ROC Curves
plot_model(tuned_lda, plot='auc')
```

The ROC curve graph presents the model with the highest precision and a random classifier for comparison. In practice, good classifiers will be above the diagonal line, and the farther away from the line, the better the system [25].

Figure 3. ROC Curves for the LDA model after the optimization process.

The command to generate the graphic of the feature importance is given by:

```
## Plotting the Feature Importance
plot_model(tuned_lda, plot='feature')
```


Figure 4. Feature importance using the estimator lightgbm for LDA model after the optimization process.

Figure 4 shows the features of greater importance for the algorithm LDA. As previously mentioned, all the plots presented in this article are easily obtained using just one line of code, but their significance goes beyond simplicity. Each plot contains highly relevant information that contributes significantly to the analysis and understanding of the results.

IV. Discussion

The data preprocessing, implementation of ML algorithms, and statistical analyses were conducted using Python version 3.10.12 as the programming language, Visual Studio Code version 1.80.1 of June 2023 as the software environment, and PyCaret version 3.0.4. The simplicity of testing multiple models with the PyCaret library allows for efficient comparison and contrast of the performance of the top three algorithms after hyperparameter optimization. This approach enables us to identify and select the most effective models for the specific task at hand, ensuring robust and reliable results in our analyses.

Analyzing the results presented in Table III, we observe that the KNN, LIGHTGBM, RIDGE, ETC, and LDA algorithms demonstrated superior performance when trained on the data, with accuracy exceeding 82% compared to the other algorithms. However, when considering the testing data

and the optimization process to which the algorithms were subjected, as shown in Table IV, the models based on the SVM-Linear, GBC, and LDA algorithms emerged as the top-performing models with the best average results.

In Figure 2, the confusion matrix for the LDA model is depicted, which achieved the best performance when applied to the test data. Notably, the matrix displays $TP = 22$, $TN = 19$, $FP = 5$, and $FN = 2$, as previously defined in Table II. Utilizing the data derived from the confusion matrix for the LDA model, various performance metrics were computed, yielding an accuracy of 85.42%, an precision of 81.48%, an recall of 91.67%, and an F1-score of 86.27%. Remarkably, the LDA model outperformed the average obtained on the training data, demonstrating a percentage increase of 3.82%, elevating the accuracy from 82.28% to 85.42%.

Furthermore, Figure 3 presents the ROC curve for the LDA model, juxtaposed against a random model with an AUC value of 0.8802. Notably, the ROC curve displays a considerable separation from the Random Model, represented by the dotted line. This outcome is highly significant, as the maximum AUC value is 1, underscoring the model's discriminative power and ability to distinguish between different classes effectively.

In Figure 4, the Feature Importance graph illustrates the key contributors to the ML model's classification of patients with PD based on acoustic features extracted from their voices. Notably, the features 'HNR35,' 'PPE,' 'MFCC3,' 'HNR15,' 'Gender,' 'Delta5,' 'MFCC10,' 'Delta2,' 'GNE,' and 'RPDE' stand out as the most influential in facilitating the LDA algorithm's ability to accurately distinguish individuals with PD. These features play a pivotal role in capturing essential patterns and characteristics within the voice data, enabling the ML model to effectively differentiate between PD patients and HC. Additionally, further refinement of data treatment was performed by modifying parameters in the tune_model function, such as employing correlation to eliminate potential collinearities between variables as proposed in [3].

V. Conclusion

In this concise study exploring ML for analyzing voice recordings of Parkinson's disease patients, we observed 16 default classification models available in the PyCaret low-code machine learning library in Python. Among them, the top three models for patient status classification in the analyzed dataset were GBC, SVM, and LDA, each achieving accuracy greater than 83%, recall greater than 83.00%, precision greater than 78.00%, and F1-Score greater than 83.00%. Notably, the LDA model improved from 82.28% accuracy on training data to 85.42% on testing data, indicating a performance variation of 3.82%. Similarly, the SVM model exhibited a remarkable increase from 76.02% accuracy on training data to 83.33% on testing data, showing a variation of 9.62%. These results highlight the simplicity and potential of low-code tools like PyCaret in showcasing the capabilities of Machine Learning libraries as valuable complements to clinical practice. Despite the relatively straightforward techniques employed, the models achieved significant performance in classifying PD patients. This suggests that Machine Learning may become clinically useful in the future for decision-making about patient clinical status,

enabling doctors and healthcare professionals to make more informed decisions and enhance the patient's quality of life.

Acknowledgment

The authors of this work are grateful to the National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq); the Coordination for the Improvement for Higher Level Personnel (CAPES); the Ministry of Science, Technology, Innovation, and Communications (MCTIC); the Research Foundation of the State of Minas Gerais (FAPEMIG); and the UCI Machine Learning Repository for making available the database used in this study. A. A. Pereira is a research productivity fellow at CNPq, Brazil (309525/2021-7).

References

- [1] J. Jankovic, "Parkinson's disease: Clinical features and diagnosis," *Journal of Neurology, Neurosurgery and Psychiatry*, vol. 79, no. 4. BMJ Publishing Group, pp. 368–376, 2008. doi: 10.1136/jnnp.2007.131045.
- [2] L. Naranjo, C. J. Pérez, Y. Campos-Roca, and J. Martín, "Addressing voice recording replications for Parkinson's disease detection," *Expert Syst Appl*, vol. 46, pp. 286–292, Mar. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.eswa.2015.10.034.
- [3] R. Z. U. Rehman, S. Del Din, Y. Guan, A. J. Yarnall, J. Q. Shi, and L. Rochester, "Selecting Clinically Relevant Gait Characteristics for Classification of Early Parkinson's Disease: A Comprehensive Machine Learning Approach," *Sci Rep*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 17269, 2019, doi: 10.1038/s41598-019-53656-7.
- [4] E. Ray Dorsey *et al.*, "Global, regional, and national burden of Parkinson's disease, 1990–2016: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2016," *Lancet Neurol*, vol. 17, no. 11, pp. 939–953, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.1016/S1474-4422(18)30295-3.
- [5] I. Karabayir, S. M. Goldman, S. Pappu, and O. Akbilgic, "Gradient boosting for Parkinson's disease diagnosis from voice recordings," *BMC Med Inform Decis Mak*, vol. 20, no. 1, p. 228, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1186/s12911-020-01250-7.
- [6] J. Bronstein, P. Carvey, H. Chen, D. Cory-Slechta, D. Dimonte, and J. Duda, "Meeting report; consensus statement-parkinson's disease and the environment; collaborative on Health and the Environment and Parkinson's action Network (CHE PAN) Conference," *Environ Health Perspect*, vol. 117, no. 1, pp. 117–121, 2009, doi: 10.1289/ehp.H702.
- [7] J. Massano and K. P. Bhatia, "Clinical approach to Parkinson's disease: Features, diagnosis, and principles of management," *Cold Spring Harb Perspect Med*, vol. 2, no. 6, 2012, doi: 10.1101/cshperspect.a008870.
- [8] A. Y. Meigal, S. M. Rissanen, M. P. Tarvainen, O. Airaksinen, M. Kankaanpää, and P. A. Karjalainen, "Non-Linear EMG Parameters for Differential and Early Diagnostics of Parkinson's Disease," *Front Neurol*, vol. 4, 2013, doi: 10.3389/fneur.2013.00135.
- [9] I. Tougui, A. Jilbab, and J. El Mhamdi, "Machine Learning Smart System for Parkinson Disease Classification Using the Voice as a Biomarker," *Healthc Inform Res*, vol. 28, no. 3, pp. 210–221, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.4258/hir.2022.28.3.210.
- [10] Z. Karapinar Senturk, "Early diagnosis of Parkinson's disease using machine learning algorithms," *Med Hypotheses*, vol. 138, p. 109603, May 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.mehy.2020.109603.
- [11] T. Hastie, R. Tibshirani, and J. Friedman, *The Elements of Statistical Learning: Data Mining, Inference, and Prediction.*, Second Edition., vol. I. Springer, 2009.
- [12] K. Arulkumaran, M. P. Deisenroth, M. Brundage, and A. A. Bharath, "A Brief Survey of Deep Reinforcement Learning," Aug. 2017, doi: 10.1109/msp.2017.2743240.
- [13] D. Dua and C. Graff, "UCI Machine Learning Repository," 2017. Accessed: Nov. 21, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml>
- [14] L. Naranjo, C. J. Pérez, J. Martín, and Y. Campos-Roca, "A two-stage variable selection and classification approach for Parkinson's disease detection by using voice recording replications," *Comput Methods Programs Biomed*, vol. 142, pp. 147–156, Apr. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.cmpb.2017.02.019.
- [15] R. Alshammri, G. Alharbi, E. Alharbi, and I. Almubark, "Machine learning approaches to identify Parkinson's disease using voice signal features," *Front Artif Intell*, vol. 6, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.3389/frai.2023.1084001.
- [16] D. Jain and V. Singh, "Feature selection and classification systems for chronic disease prediction: A review," *Egyptian Informatics Journal*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 179–189, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.eij.2018.03.002.
- [17] C. Jatoth, N. E., M. A. V. R., and S. R. Annaluri, "Effective monitoring and prediction of Parkinson disease in Smart Cities using intelligent health care system," *Microprocess Microsyst*, vol. 92, p. 104547, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.micpro.2022.104547.
- [18] G. Tolios, *Simplifying Machine Learning with PyCaret A Low-code Approach for Beginners and Experts!*, 1st ed., vol. 1. Leanpub book, 2022.
- [19] Moez Ali, "PyCaret: An open source, low-code machine learning library in Python," Apr. 2020. <https://www.pycaret.org> (accessed Jan. 28, 2023).
- [20] D. A. GIL and M. B. JOHNSON, "Diagnosing Parkinson by using Artificial Neural Networks and Support Vector Machines," *Global Journal of Computer Science and Technology*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 63–71, 2009, Accessed: Jul. 24, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.182.7856&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
- [21] R. Das, "A comparison of multiple classification methods for diagnosis of Parkinson disease," *Expert Syst Appl*, vol. 37, no. 2, pp. 1568–1572, Mar. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.eswa.2009.06.040.
- [22] G. Bao, M. Lin, X. Sang, Y. Hou, Y. Liu, and Y. Wu, "Classification of Dysphonic Voices in Parkinson's Disease with Semi-Supervised Competitive Learning Algorithm," *Biosensors (Basel)*, vol. 12, no. 7, p. 502, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.3390/bios12070502.
- [23] D. Joshi, A. Khajuria, and P. Joshi, "An automatic non-invasive method for Parkinson's disease classification," *Comput Methods Programs Biomed*, vol. 145, pp. 135–145, Jul. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.cmpb.2017.04.007.
- [24] R. C. Blair and R. A. Taylor, *Bioestatística para ciências da saúde*, vol. 1. São Paulo: Pearson, 2013.
- [25] R. C. Prati, G. E. de A. P. A. Batista, and M. C. Monard, "Curvas ROC para avaliação de classificadores," *IEEE Latin America Transactions*, 2008.